

APPLICATION OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SUBJECT “ART OF THE BALLET MASTER”

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19177270>

Abstract: This article examines the use of innovative and information technologies in education, which have a real impact on the effectiveness not only of the educational process but also on the formation of systematic knowledge and generalized skills in the specialty of a choreographic group leader.

Keywords: information, digital technologies, idea, theory, science, music, choreography, dance, choreographer, analysis, composition.

Obtaining quality education is considered the main priority and value in our country, and currently it is an area of activity for specialists with higher education. Therefore, the education system must meet certain requirements, ensure the ability to assimilate the flow of modern information, and develop skills of research activity, individual and independent work. Every profession assume a certain base of knowledge, skills, and abilities, without which one cannot be considered a specialist in the chosen field. Creative professions are no exception in this regard. At the current stage of societal development, when modern telecommunication systems perform the functions of effective educational technical tools, scientific and technological progress has led to intensive growth and renewal of scientific and technical information.

Dance is an instrument of social physical and spiritual education, where the dance image is one of the forms of reflecting reality and has objective cognitive and educational significance.

Engaging in the creative process and creating dance productions, the choreographer influences emotional culture and aesthetic education of society as a whole through choreographic art. However, with the growth of technical equipment, “spectacle” comes to the forefront of dance production, which requires the choreographer to have certain knowledge in the field of digital technologies. In choreographic art, the use of digital technologies involves their application in all types of activities: teaching, management, and creative work. The profession of a choreographer-director is not only creative. It suppose knowledge and solutions to a wide range of issues, professional competence, creative thinking, and, of course, mastery of the profession.

Developing a student's natural talents and providing necessary knowledge and skills is one of the main features of training specialists in choreographic groups. However, knowing the principles of choreography and being able to implement them in one's creative work are different things. Everything begins with an idea—the initial concept of a future choreographic work. This is the task that initiates the creative research for the right solution. But before solving such a global task, a modern choreographer must master not only the basics of composition and staging but also the skills of properly using digital technologies. Digital technologies are a rapidly changing environment with constant innovations. Today, new technologies are actively being introduced into all spheres of society. Regardless of the field, due to convenience, openness, and speed of information transfer, digital technologies have become an important factor in updating and transmitting information. Technological development requires the introduction of new approaches to education that ensure the development of communicative, creative, and professional knowledge, as well as the need for self-education. A problem faced by many young choreographers today is the vast flow of visual information that must be theoretically comprehended and properly selected. Traditionally, knowledge was passed practically from master to student. Practice must be supported by scientific theory. Therefore, choreographers, especially young specialists, must be able to combine scientific and creative work with research activity, which helps reveal individual creative abilities and develops systematic work skills. The role of the information space in the educational system is mainly related to cognitive learning functions. One of the ways to use the full potential of the human body is visual-modular learning based on the principle “from simple to complex.”

In our profession, we must be able to imagine choreographic images and convey ideas to the audience through expressive dance language. In the process of creating a new choreographic work, the choreographer's creative imagination plays a huge role. It manifests not only in composing dance scenes but also in developing the plot, creating composition plans, and building images that reveal the main idea of the work.

The main goals of education are to teach students to find the right ways of self-expression and to implement their ideas in reality through choreography. Digital technologies have a real opportunity to influence not only the effectiveness of the educational process but also the formation of systematic knowledge and professional skills. Thus, a whole system of learning and scientific research is formed, necessary for the development of new technologies. In conclusion,

choreography today has developed its own system of expressive means and a special connection with music. Dance gives viewers incomparable enjoyment of harmony, beauty, and plasticity. Combined with digital technologies, it allows deeper immersion into the artistic work.

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